

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 1*H*-PYRAZOLO[3,4-*b*]PYRIDINE DERIVATIVES (3)

Sl. no.	5-Amino-pyrazole (in g)	Prop-2-en-1-one (in g)	M p. °C	X	Y	R ¹	R ²	R ³	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
										C	H	N
3a	2.6	2.9	145	H	Cl	Cl	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ Cl ₂ F ₂ N ₃	68.14 (68.18)	3.18 (3.21)	7.89 (7.95)
b	2.5	2.4	190	F	H	H	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₆ F ₃ N ₃	75.40 (75.47)	3.68 (3.77)	8.76 (8.80)
c	2.5	2.5	210	F	H	ClH ₂	F	F	C ₃₁ H ₂₀ F ₃ N ₃	75.71 (75.76)	4.01 (4.07)	8.48 (8.55)
d	2.5	2.7	240	F	H	Cl	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ ClF ₂ N ₃	70.31 (70.38)	3.29 (3.32)	8.17 (8.21)
e	2.5	2.2	223	F	H	H	F	H	C ₃₀ H ₁₉ F ₂ N ₃	78.34 (78.40)	4.09 (4.13)	9.10 (9.15)
f	2.5	2.7	200	F	H	CH ₃	F	Cl	C ₃₁ H ₂₀ ClF ₂ N ₃	73.25 (73.30)	3.89 (3.94)	8.20 (8.27)
g	3.3	2.2	215	F	Br	H	F	H	C ₃₀ H ₁₈ BrF ₂ N ₃	66.86 (66.90)	3.29 (3.34)	7.71 (7.80)
h	3.3	2.4	220	F	Br	H	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₇ Br ₂ N ₃	64.69 (64.74)	3.01 (3.05)	7.47 (7.55)
i	3.3	2.5	175	F	Br	CH ₃	F	F	C ₃₁ H ₁₉ BrF ₂ N ₃	65.21 (65.26)	3.29 (3.33)	7.30 (7.36)
j	3.3	2.7	185	F	Br	Cl	F	F	C ₃₀ H ₁₆ BrClF ₂ N ₃	61.00 (61.01)	2.68 (2.71)	7.07 (7.11)

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1,3-Dioxolo[4,5-*g*]quinazolines

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KEEPING in view the physiological importance of 1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]quinazolines, some authors have reported^{1,2} the synthesis of 6-methyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]quinazolin-8(*7H*)-one (2a). Here we report a one-step synthesis of the same compound by the direct condensation of methyl-6-aminopiperonylate (1)³ with acetonitrile in the presence of dry HCl. Furthermore, a phenyl group has also been introduced in this system at position-6 by treating 1 with benzonitrile.

In the second approach, a phenyl group has been introduced in this system at position-7 by treating 1 with triethylorthoformate followed by the cyclisation of the intermediate, methyl-6-[(ethoxymethylene)amino]piperonylate (3) with aniline.

In the third approach, 6-methylthio/ethylthio-7-phenyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]quinazolin-8(*7H*)-ones (2d-e) have been synthesised by the condensation of 1 with phenyl isothiocyanate followed by reaction with methyl iodide or with ethyl bromide in the

presence of sodium hydroxide. In yet another approach, 1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-6,8(5H,7H)-dione (5) has been prepared by the condensation of 1 with urea and found identical with the product earlier prepared by the condensation of 6-amino-piperonylic acid with KOCN by Hess *et al.*⁴. It

- a, R=CH₃, R'=H
 b, R=C₆H₅, R'=H
 c, R=H, R'=C₆H₅
 d, R=SCH₃, R'=C₆H₅
 e, R=SC₂H₅, R'=C₆H₅

spectra (nujol) of 5 (not reported earlier) showed characteristic bands at 1 642 (N-CO-N), 1 670 (CO-N) and 3 190, 3 350 cm⁻¹ (N-H's). The chemical shifts of all these compounds were compatible with their structures.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Varian EM 390 90MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference (chemical shifts in δ ppm).

6-Methyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-8(7H) one (2a): Dry HCl was passed through a solution of 1 (0.40 g) in acetonitrile (5 ml) with constant stirring at room temperature for 1 h. The contents were kept overnight. Excess of acetonitrile was removed under reduced pressure and the residue triturated with ethanol (2 ml) and collected by filtration under suction. The product was crystallised from ethanol, (0.34 g, 81%), m.p. > 300° (Found: C, 58.51; H, 3.83; N, 13.89. C₁₀H₉N₂O₂ requires: C, 58.82; H, 3.92; N, 13.75%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 350 (N-H) and 1 660 (CO-N) cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃+TFA) 7.70 (1H, s, C₈-H), 7.27 (1H, s, C₄-H), 6.37 (2H, s, OCH₂O) and 2.93 (3H, s, CH₃).

6-Phenyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-8(7H)-one (2b): Following the above procedure, it was prepared by the reaction of 1 with benzonitrile, and

crystallised from ethanol, (76%), m.p. 291° (Found: N, 0.39. C₁₅H₁₀N₂O₂ requires: N, 10.53%); δ (CDCl₃ + TFA) 8.20-7.60 (6H, m, =C-C₆H₅+C₈-H), 7.40 (1H, s, C₄-H) and 6.35 (2H, s, OCH₂O).

Methyl-6-[(ethoxymethylene)amino]piperonylate (3): A solution of 1 (1.95 g, 0.01 mol) in triethylorthoformate (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 h, excess triethylorthoformate was distilled off under reduced pressure and the residual mass extracted with hot petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). The petroleum ether extract on concentration furnished a solid which on filtration and crystallisation from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) gave 3 (1.51 g, 60%), m.p. 180-2° (Found: C, 57.57; H, 5.00; N, 5.48. C₁₅H₁₃NO₅ requires: C, 57.37; H, 5.18; N, 5.58%); δ (CDCl₃) 7.52 (2H, d, C₈-H+N=CH), 6.46 (1H, s, C₆-H), 6.11 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 4.43 (2H, q, OCH₂CH₃), 3.90 (3H, s, COOCH₃) and 1.42 (3H, t, OC₂CH₃).

7-Phenyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-8(7H)-one (2c): Aniline (0.2 ml, 0.002 mol) was added to a solution of 3 (0.5 g, 0.002 mol) in ethanol (20 ml), and the contents were refluxed on a steam-bath for 6 h. Ethanol was distilled off and the residue after washing with water was crystallised from ethanol to give 2c (0.38 g, 72%), m.p. 209-10° (Found: C, 67.87; H, 3.60; N, 10.47. C₁₅H₁₀N₂O₂ requires: C, 67.67; H, 3.76; N, 10.53%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 035, 1 672, 1 575, 1 450, 1 372, 1 270, 1 28, 1 045, 970, 920, 852, 785, 745 and 682 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 8.20 (1H, s, =CH), 7.80 (1H, s, C₈-H), 7.63 (5H, m, N-C₆H₅), 7.23 (1H, s, C₄-H) and 6.23 (2H, s, OCH₂O).

5,6-Dihydro-7-phenyl-6-thio-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-8(7H)-one (4): A mixture of 1 (1.95 g, 0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (1.25 ml) was heated on a water-bath for 45 min. The contents first became mobile and then solidified. The product was triturated with a little ethanol and collected under suction. Crystallisation from ethanol gave 4 (2.56 g, 86%), m.p. > 300° (Found: C, 60.26; H, 3.50; N, 9.63. C₁₅H₁₀N₂O₂S requires: C, 60.40; H, 3.36; N, 9.40%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 210, 1 660, 1 530, 1 460, 1 372, 1 235, 1 120, 1 035, 920, 890, 850, 747 and 682 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃+TFA) 7.73-7.20 (6H, m, N-C₆H₅+C₈-H), 6.93 (1H, s, C₄-H) and 6.23 (2H, s, OCH₂O).

6-Methylthio-7-phenyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-8(7H)-one (2d): To a solution of 4 (1.49 g, 0.005 mol) in 5% sodium hydroxide (4 ml, 0.005 mol), methyl iodide (0.35 ml, 0.005 mol) dissolved in ethanol (10 ml) was added dropwise with stirring at room temperature. There was immediate separation of a solid. After keeping overnight, the mixture was diluted with water; and the solid collected under suction, was washed with water and crystallised from ethanol to yield 2d (1.20 g,

77%), m.p. 205° (Found: C, 61.39; H, 3.90; N, 8.82. $C_{16}H_{13}N_2O_3S$ requires: C, 61.54; H, 3.85; N, 8.97%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 662, 1 535, 1 447, 1 375, 1 300, 1 272, 1 235, 1 168, 1 028, 920, 865, 755 and 628 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.76–7.33 (6H, m, N–C₆H₅ + C₉–H), 7.10 (1H, s, C₄–H), 6.16 (2H, s, OCH₂O) and 2.53 (3H, s, SCH₃).

6-Ethylthio-7-phenyl-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-8(7H)-one (2e): It was prepared by the above procedure by using ethyl bromide instead of methyl iodide. The product was crystallised from ethanol, yield (67%), m.p. 223° (Found: N, 8.48. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2O_3S$ requires: N, 8.59%); δ ($CDCl_3$) 7.67–7.26 (6H, m, N–C₆H₅ + C₉–H), 7.00 (1H, s, C₄–H), 6.10 (2H, s, OCH₂O), 3.13 (2H, q, SCH₂CH₃) and 1.33 (3H, t, SCH₂CH₃).

1,3-Dioxolo[4,5-g]quinazolin-6,8(5H,7H)-dione (5): A mixture of **1** (1.95 g, 0.01 mol) and urea (3.0 g, 0.05 mol) was heated in an oil-bath at 110–15° for 30 min. The temperature was then raised to 150–60°. There was evolution of ammonia which ceased after 7–8 h. It was then cooled and the product crystallised from ethanol, (1.69 g, 82%), m.p. >300° (Found: C, 52.62; H, 2.99; N, 13.45. $C_9H_6N_2O_4$ requires: C, 52.42; H, 2.91; N, 13.59%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 350, 3 190 (N–H's), 1 670 (CO–N) and 1 642 (N–CO–N) cm^{-1} .

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Ursolic Acid from *Nepeta leucophylla* Benth.

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MANY plants, including members of the genus *Nepeta*, have been reported to yield ursolic acid **1a** often in combination with its isomer oleanolic acid **1b**^{1–3}. We describe here the isolation

and identification of 98% pure **1a** as its monohydrate from *N. leucophylla* Benth.

1a; R₁=H; R₂=CH₃
1b; R₁=CH₃; R₂=H

The leaves of *N. leucophylla* were collected from Nainital in the month of May. Identification was confirmed by Y. P. S. Pangtey, Kumaun University (Herbarium no. 708) and P. P. Mnyal, F.R.I., Dehradun (Accession no. 153826). The dried and powdered leaves (785 g) were extracted with diethyl ether to yield a white microcrystalline product (1.7 g, 0.2%), m.p. 262–63° with gas evolution, m.p. 237–89° after drying at 110° in vacuum, $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ 64.2° (c 0.8, 1 N alc. KOH). Tlc (silica gel G; 5% CH₃OH in CHCl₃) indicated the presence of no more than one compound. The EIHR mass spectrum of the product indicated that it is **1a**, **1b** or a combination of the two⁴, and its elemental analysis and melting behavior suggested that it is **1a**.H₂O⁵. Its ir spectrum was in good agreement with that reported⁶ for **1a** and its 360 MHz ¹H nmr spectrum was consistent with the reported 60MHz spectra of related urs-12-enes^{6,7}. The 360MHz spectrum allows us to give more accurate values of δ 0.946 and 0.860, *J* 6.4Hz, for the doublets due to methyls at C₂₉ and C₃₀. Further, lack of absorption of δ 1.15 due to the C₂₇ methyl of olean-12-enes related to **1b**⁶, allows us to place an upper limit of 2% on the amount of **1b** in the *N. leucophylla* product. Resonance frequencies in the ¹³C nmr spectrum, with the exception of that due to the nondiagnostic carboxyl carbon, differed by no more than 0.3 ppm from resonances reported for methyl ursolate⁸.

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